

Short communication

Effects of different organic manure brewery spent grain and kitchen waste compost on the growth of *Albizia lebbbeck* (L.) Benth seedlings

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Abstract

The study examined the comparative study of the effects of the different organic manure brewery spent grain and kitchen waste compost on the growth of *Albizia lebbbeck*. The experiment was carried out within the premises of Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan. Twenty (20) seedlings of *Albizia lebbbeck* were selected and transplanted into polythene pots, one pot served as a control for the experimental setup. The treatments were: T1-2kg of topsoil plus 13.5g of brewery spent grain, T3-2kg of topsoil plus 13.5g of kitchen waste compost, T4- combination of the kitchen waste compost and brewery spent grain with 2kg of topsoil and T2-topsoil only. The experiment was laid out in a complete randomized design (CRD) with four treatments replicate five times each making 20 samples over a period of 12 weeks. Data were collected on the following parameters: plant height (cm), Collar diameter (mm) and Branch production. Data collected were later subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at the 5 % level of probability. The result shows that treatment 3: (kitchen waste compost) had the highest in the parameter assessed in term of plant height, collar diameter with the mean value of 13.85±0.34 (cm) and 2.02±0.01 (mm), while treatment 2: (control) has the least performance in all the parameters assessed plant height, collar diameter and branch production with their means of value of 10.34±0.41(cm), 1.89±0.01(mm) and 5±0.63. In samples T1 and T4 there were no much significant difference among the parameters assessed. It can therefore be concluded that T3 of 2kg of topsoil plus 13.5g of kitchen waste compost had the best positive effect on the growth of *Albizia lebbbeck* seedlings. Base on the result kitchen waste compost can therefore be recommended for the growth and production of *Albizia lebbbeck* at nursery stage.

Keywords: Organic manure, grains, topsoil, *Albizia lebbbeck*, seedlings

Received: 22/02/18

Accepted: 17/04/18

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Introduction

Forest is a large area of land covered with trees or other woody vegetation. Hundreds of more precise definitions of forest are used throughout the world, incorporating factors such as tree density, tree height, land use, legal standing and ecological function. According to the widely used United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization definition, forests covered four billion hectares (15 million square miles) or approximately 30 percent of the world's land area in 2006. Forests are the dominant terrestrial ecosystem on Earth and are distributed across the globe. Forests account for 75% of the gross primary productivity of the Earth's biosphere and contain 80% of the Earth's plant biomass.

The soil is an adequate physical, chemical, and biological medium of plant growth, which supports the life of a plant, (Salt, 2007). The soil provides the essential nutrient required for plant development. It contains a range of micro-organisms that break plant wastes and help the plant to absorb nutrient from the soil. It also includes trace element which is nutrient in nature for the benefit of surviving of plant the element include nitrogen, potassium, etc. present in the soil and they are needed in large quantity by the plant (Chanye *et al.*, 2007).

Kitchen wastes compost is an organic material which is naturally made, it is an important process that returns valuable nutrients to the soil for plants to use. Composting is a tool that allows us to control and accelerate this natural process. Aside from benefiting our soil, a well-maintained compost pile can reduce the amount of yard and food wastes that are sent to landfills each year. According to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Americans produce more than four pounds of wastes per person per day (or 1,600 pounds per person per year). The EPA estimates that 65 percent of that waste is organic and could be composted into a rich material that can improve the soil and enhance the growth of lawns and gardens (EPA, 2000). Adding compost to the soil can help supplement chemical fertilizers. Compost can even partially replace chemical fertilizers, but one should test the soil and plant tissues before doing so.

Brewery spent grain also known as brewers draft consists of the residue of malt and grain, which remain in the mash-kettle after mashing and lustering process (Beldman *et al.*, 2004). It consists primarily of grain husks, pericarp, and fragment of endosperm. As it mainly consists of carbohydrates and protein, it is readily consumed by animals.

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(Forsell, 2008). Brewery spent grain can also be used as a fertilizer, whole grain in bread, as well, in the production of biogas (Peter Reinhart, 2007). Brewer spent grain is also an ideal medium for growing mushrooms, such as take and already some breweries are either own mushroom or supply spent grain mushroom farms storm brewing. Therefore, the study is aimed at determining the effect of different organic manure brewery spent grain and kitchen waste compost on the growth of *Albizia lebeck* seedlings

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out at the screen-house of Federal College of Forestry, Jericho, Ibadan (latitude 7°23'N and longitude 3°51'E). The site was situated at Jericho area in Ibadan North West Local Government of Oyo State, Nigeria. It is characterized by two distinct seasons, which are dry seasons (November to March) and raining season (April to October) with mean annual raining rainfall of 1400 - 1500mm and average relative of 80% - 85% (FRIN, 2015).

Procurement of Materials

Albizia lebeck seeds were collected from the school entrance of Federal College of Forestry, Jericho Ibadan, the brewery spent grain (SPG) was collected from the Nigeria brewery industry, New Ife Road, Ibadan. The kitchen wastes were collected from the Iya Bunmi food canteen, within the school premises which comprises (Banana peels, Eggshells, potato peeled, beans shaft and yam peels). The topsoil was collected from the arboretum in the college premises.

Method

The topsoil was air-dried and sieved with a 2mm sieve; this was to remove gravel and pebbles that may affect the growth of seedlings and the organic manure already collected. The kitchen compost materials were gathered in a bucket mixed together and it was wet daily for easy soften of the kitchen wastes compost. The organic manure (brewery spent grain and kitchen wastes compost) were thoroughly mixed with top soil at the level of 13.5g of brewery spent grain and kitchen wastes compost to 2kg of top soil and the control to form four (4) different treatment, T1 (2kg of topsoil + 13.5g of brewery spent grain), T2 2kg of top soil (control), (2kg of top soil + 13.5g of kitchen wastes compost), and T4 (2kg of top soil + 13.5g kitchen wastes compost + 13.5g brewery spent grain). Which were replicated 5 times, making a total of 20 pots.

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Experimental Layout

T1R3	T4R1	T2R3	T3R5	T2R1
T4R3	T2R5	T1R1	T3R1	T2R4
T3R2	T1R5	T4R2	T2R2	T1R2
T3R5	T4R4	T3R4	T1R4	T4R5

Parameters Assessed

1. Plant height (cm): The heights of the seedlings were measured with ruler graduated in centimeters from the soil level to the top of terminal bud.
2. Stem girth (mm): it was measured using a vernier caliper graduated in millimeter.
3. Branch production: was done via counting.

Data Analysis

The data collected were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the means that were found to be significant were separated by least significant difference (LSD) at 5% level of probability.

Results and Discussions

Plant height

The results revealed that there were significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the effect of the organic manure on the mean of the plant height growth of *Albizia lebbek* seedlings as presented in Table 1. The plant height of *Albizia lebbek* seedlings in kitchen wastes composts (T_3) had the highest value of 13.85cm. While plants height of *Albizia lebbek* seedlings in (T_2) control had the least value of 10.34cm. The mean separation showed that the plant height of seedlings in T_1 and T_4 are not significantly different from each other as presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Effect of Organic Manure on the Growth of *Albizia lebbbeck* Seedlings

Parameter	SV	Df	SS	MS	F	Sig.
Height (cm)	Treatment	3	31.31	10.44	9.26	0.00*
	Error	16	18.05	1.13		
	Total	19	49.36			
Collar Diameter (mm)	Treatment	3	0.05	0.02	11.78	0.00*
	Error	16	0.02	0.00		
	Total	19	0.07			
Leaf Production	Treatment	3	5.01	1.67	1.56	0.24 ^{ns}
	Error	16	17.13	1.07		
	Total	19	22.14			

*Significant at ($p \leq 0.05$) ns - not significant ($p > 0.05$)

Stem diameter

The results revealed that there is a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the effect of the organic manure on the mean diameter of *Albizia lebbbeck* seedlings as shown in Table 1. The mean values showed that the stem diameter of *Albizia lebbbeck* seedlings in (T₃) have the highest value of 2.02mm, while the stem diameter of *Albizia lebbbeck* seedlings in (T₂) has the lowest values of 1.89mm. The mean separation showed that the stem diameter of seedlings in T₁, T₂, T₄ are not significantly different from each other as revealed in Table 2.

Table 2: Growth Mean Values of *A. lebbbeck* seedlings

Organic Manure	Height (cm)	Collar Diameter (mm)	Leaf Production
T1	12.48±0.55ab	1.91±0.02b	6±0.40
T2	10.34±0.41c	1.89±0.01b	5±0.63
T3	13.85±0.34a	2.02±0.01a	6±0.45
T4	12.26±0.56b	1.94±0.02b	6±0.30

Mean±SE followed by the same superscripts in each column are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$)

Branch Production

The result reveals that there was no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the effect of the organic manure on the mean branch count of *Albizia lebbbeck* seedlings as presented in Table 1, while the branch count of *Albizia lebbbeck* seedlings in T₁, T₃ and T₄ are not significantly different from each other with the mean value of 6 as revealed in Table 2.

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Conclusion

Judging from the growth response of *Albizia lebbeck*, there was a steady rise in growth in terms of plant height, stem diameter, and branch production. This shows that there is a significant difference in the parameters assessed. In plant height, T3 had the highest mean value of 13.85cm, while T2 had the least performance of mean value of 10.34cm, in collar diameter T2 performed better in the treatments with the mean value of 2.02mm while T3 had the least performance in the collar diameter with the mean value of 1.89mm. This shows that it is significantly different in term of plant height and collar diameter within the weeks and except for branch production that shows no significant difference among treatments. The difference in the treatments was significant at 5% level in plant height, collar diameter and was not significant at 5% level in branch production. Therefore, it could be concluded that the treatments had a different impact on soil productivity.

Recommendations

Based on the results obtained from the findings. This study showed that T3 (kitchen wastes compost) performed better on all parameters assessed. It is therefore recommended that farmers and silviculturists should make use of kitchen wastes compost for optimum production of *Albizia lebbeck* seedlings at nursery stag.

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